

3.6 SLR results

3.6.1 RQ.1 What are the main points of similarity and difference between the data protection laws of Brazil, the European Union, the USA and Australia?

The studies present the most diverse points of convergence and divergence, dealing with the scope of the law - identifying personal data and the parties involved in the processing -, the specific legal definitions of each law, individual rights, principles and, as a consequence of non-compliance, administrative sanctions. Studies related to the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) are easily found, including comparisons with the General Data Protection Law (LGPD) itself. The biggest obstacle was identifying studies that related the American legislation - the American Data Privacy and Protection Act (ADPPA) - to the others, since it is the most recent of the objects of study in this work. To meet this need, results on California's privacy law - the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) - were also extracted, given their legal and regional similarities.

With regard to scope, one factor of similarity between the LGPD and GDPR is *opt-in* oriented consent (E9[69], E10[18]), i.e. data subjects make it explicit that they accept the processing before it begins (through policies involving terms of use or *cookies*). Not only that, but consent itself is considered an individual right under both laws. That said, one topic of divergence in relation to Brazilian and European law, is the *opt-out* style consent carried out by the CCPA (E2[29], E18[73]).

The guarantee, by law, that individuals' personal data will be protected is unanimous, although US and Canadian legislation has a focus on companies and employees (E1[13], E14[21], E25[46]), which points to a greater prioritization of corporate freedom than of an individual's privacy rights (E3[47]). Thus, an important point of divergence in this area is that employees' personal data, for example, is not covered by the ADPPA, whereas it is covered by the GDPR (E14[21]).

When it comes to territorial scope, the LGPD and the GDPR are similar, in that even if the organizations are not physically located in Brazil or the European Union, respectively, the legislation may still be applicable, and it is only necessary that they offer services or process citizens' data (E10[18], E21[41]). In this way, despite the need for a greater degree of supervision, the GDPR

has among the laws the greatest autonomy for its regulatory agencies, due to the greater legal and theoretical framework available, even when compared to other laws (E4[40], E15[71]).

As far as sensitive personal data is concerned, all the legislations have a special category defining it (E14[21], E32[83], E43[7], E47[49]), which is a mark of similarity, and their definitions are similar, such as racial or ethnic origin, political opinion and health data. However, the specification of sensitive data presented by the ADPPA is more explanatory than the GDPR (E14[21]), and consequently, than the LGPD. In addition, information that contributes to the identification of an individual (not directly) is considered sensitive data in the GDPR, while the association is merely direct in the LGPD (E32[83]). It is worth remembering that, as explained in Section 2.1, a distinguishing point of Australian law is that it considers an opinion about an individual to be personal data.

Most laws - LGPD, GDPR, ADPPA and CCPA - specify entities responsible for processing personal data (E1[13], E8[45], E12[70], E14[21], E41[22]) and also identify them by classes such as operator, controller, *Data Protection Officer* (DPO) in the GDPR (E26[17], E33[84]), processor, etc.

As far as definitions are concerned, a point of divergence emerges when identifying that the individuals who are supported by the legislation point out that the GDPR is more inclusive than the CCPA and the ADPPA (E7[68], E14[21], E22[76], E25[46]), since the latter only includes citizens residing in the United States, while the CCPA only considers data involved in financial transactions. Not only that, but Australian privacy law has the smallest coverage area when compared to the GDPR (E47[49]), to the point of reinforcing the idea that the GDPR has a more complete scope in guaranteeing privacy.

Another point of divergence is regarding children's consent to data processing: in the GDPR, children cannot consent, while in the CCPA, consent is free from the age of 13 (E50[37]).

Regarding the life cycle of personal data, there are some notable similarities and differences between the GDPR, the CCPA and the ADPPA (E8[45]): collection is minimized in the European and North American laws, but is more flexible in the California legislation (it is enough to notify the holders); transfer is different in the three laws, since it is oriented to the user's objection in the GDPR, allowed by de-identified data in the ADPPA and allowed merely by prior notice in the CCPA; processing is similar in the GDPR and the ADPPA, only consistent with the purposes, while in the CCPA only pseudonymization is required; and retention differs, such that it is consistent with the purposes in the GDPR, as a rule at the end of the service or when required by law in the ADPPA and based on the user's request in the CCPA (despite presenting the right to

exclusion evidenced (E18[73])), which again highlights the *opt-out* process.

In addition to the LGPD and GDPR presenting a series of equivalent individual rights and principles (E9[69], E10[18]), some of these bases alternate, i.e. the principles of free access, prevention and non-discrimination established by the LGPD are not directly equivalent to any principle of the GDPR, since they are covered by individual rights in European legislation (E28[43]). Likewise, Australian legislation establishes rights similar to GDPR (E17[44]), but does not present rights to restrict processing, data portability or opposition to automated decision-making.

As for comparisons between the principles, the LGPD presents ten fundamental principles and the GDPR seven (E10[18]) and, although they are similar to each other, some works still disagree about their equivalence: there is clarification that the GDPR principles of lawfulness, fairness and transparency, as well as storage limitation, have no direct equivalence with any other principle of the LGPD (E5[36]), while there is a comparative table that relates them to the principles of transparency and necessity (E28[43]). Thus, depending on the reference, these points can be considered similar or different. An important aspect of divergence is that in the GDPR anonymization is not explicitly considered a principle - similarly to the LGPD - but in Australian legislation it is (E17[44]).

Finally, the studies identified a point of divergence in terms of the administrative sanctions applied by the GDPR and those applied by the CCPA, which, as a rule, state that under European law, infringements can result in fines of up to 20 million euros or 4% of an organization's global turnover (E7[68], E16[72], E21[41], E25[46]). In the CCPA, on the other hand, fines for non-compliance are for each violation (up to 7500 dollars per violation, with no limit on the number of violations) (E7[68]) and statutory damages range from 100 to 750 dollars (E25[46]). Thus, depending on the number of violations, the sanctions imposed by the CCPA can exceed the amounts recorded in the GDPR. Under the LGPD, simple fines of up to 2% of turnover are common, limited to 50 million reais (E4[40]).

Table 3.7 shows the main points of similarity and difference addressed in the studies. The framework analysis process to be adopted aims to fill in the missing gaps in order to make an effective comparison between the laws and associate them with the frameworks.

Table 3.7: Comparisons between laws.

Theme	LGPD	GDPR	ADPPA	Privacy Act	CCPA
Personal Scope	<i>Opt-in</i> consent; emphasis on data protection	<i>Opt-in</i> consent; Focus on data protection (wide scope); Children cannot consent	<i>Opt-out</i> consent; emphasis on corporate freedom	<i>Opt-in</i> consent; Focus on data protection (less comprehensive); No differentiation between data controllers	<i>Opt-out</i> consent; Emphasis on corporate freedom; Children can consent from the age of 13
Territorial Scope	Applies to organizations in Brazil or abroad, as long as they process Brazilian data	It applies to organizations in EU or outside, as long as it processes European data	Applies only to the processing of data of individuals residing in the United States.	Applies to APP entities (organizations) that may or may not be in Australia	It applies to any for-profit entity doing business in California
Material Scope	Sensitive personal data (direct association)	Sensitive personal data (direct and indirect association); Includes personal data of employees	Sensitive personal data; does not include personal data of employees	Sensitive personal data; Considers opinion as personal data	Sensitive personal data; does not include personal data of employees
Definitions	Defines those responsible for processing (controller, operator and foreman)	Defines those responsible for processing (controller, processor and DPO)	Defines those responsible for treatment (covered entities and service providers)	Define APP entities	Define businesses and service providers
Rights	Consent and Choice; Confirmation of the existence of data; Access to data; Correction of data; Anonymization; Elimination of unnecessary data; Access to information from participating entities; Portability of data; Revocation of consent	Consent and Choice; Minimized Collection; Objection-Oriented Transfer; Processing Consistent with Purposes; Retention Consistent with Purposes; Rights to Restrict Processing, Data Portability and Objection to Automated Decision-Making	Minimized collection; Transfer oriented to identified data; Processing consistent with purpose; Retention at end of service or required by law	No rights to restrict processing, data portability and opposition to automated decision-making	Flexible collection; Notice-oriented transfer; Free termination provided there is pseudonymization; Retention based on user request
Principles	10 fundamental principles; Equivalence with principles of lawfulness, fairness and transparency and storage limitation is discussed; Anonymization is not a principle	7 fundamental principles; No equivalence with principles of free access, prevention and non-discrimination; Anonymization is not a principle	-	13 fundamental principles; Anonymization is a principle	-
Sanctions	2% of turnover (limited to 50 million reais) or daily fine	20 million euros or 4% of global turnover	No specifically defined administrative fines, but organizations that violate the ADPPA may still be subject to government enforcement actions and private rights of action	-	7500 dollars per violation and statutory damages between 100 and 750 dollars

RQ.1 Summary: The GDPR is the law with the greatest scope and coverage of personal data protection among the laws analyzed - followed by the LGPD - since it has a high level of legal maturity compared to the others. Although the ADPPA is the most recent, the economic focus sometimes overrides the right to privacy (as does the CCPA) and Australian law (the oldest), in turn, has a narrow scope when compared to current laws.

3.6.2 RQ.2 What are the challenges and techniques presented by organizations and developers when adapting to data protection laws in Brazil, the European Union, the USA and Australia?

Initially, several challenges were identified, ranging from the domain of organizations to developers, in order to achieve compliance with multiple legislations. Canedo et al. (E10[18]) and Machado et al. (E11[4]) elucidate most of the classes of challenges to be highlighted, referring to the LGPD and GDPR, respectively.

From all the selected studies, 168 isolated challenges were identified and, once categorized into classes based on the similarity of these challenges, 18 classes were obtained, as shown in Table 3.8, and ordered by quantity - which will be discussed below:

Table 3.8: Challenges presented by organizations and developers in the process of complying with privacy legislation.

ID	Challenge	Reference	Qty.
D1	Lack of knowledge of the law	[18],[13],[67],[15],[72],[44],[74],[41],[78],[17],[43],[80],[85],[7],[94],[89],[90],[91],[95],[37],[69]	21
D2	Translating law into technical context	[18],[4],[13],[13],[15],[72],[78],[17],[79],[86],[94],[90],[16],[69],[22],[92]	16
D3	Budget restrictions	[18],[4],[67],[72],[74],[78],[80],[84],[86],[7],[94],[95],[68],[82]	14
D4	Lack of staff with expertise	[4],[74],[41],[80],[84],[87],[79],[7],[94],[91],[95],[60],[82],[83]	14
D5	Organizational structure	[18],[67],[41],[17],[80],[87],[86],[88],[7],[93],[90],[91],[69],[22]	14
D6	Ambiguity of the law	[4],[70],[15],[72],[44],[41],[80],[93],[94],[60],[95],[96],[97]	13
D7	Lack of standardization of techniques/tools	[18],[17],[80],[86],[7],[89],[90],[95],[97],[98],[83]	11
D8	Lack of security/privacy policy	[18],[80],[86],[91],[37],[16],[75],[77],[82],[83]	10
D9	Relationship with the user	[80],[84],[86],[7],[93],[90],[68],[69],[75]	9
D10	Prioritization of functional requirements	[4],[78],[41],[80],[84],[7],[94],[90]	8
D11	Uncertainty of organizational processes	[4],[84],[81],[86],[93],[60],[77],[22]	8
D12	Difficulties with third-party services	[4],[84],[86],[91],[37],[16],[68]	7
D13	Shortage of guides/tools	[18],[13],[78],[7],[98]	5
D14	International data processing	[4],[13],[15],[93],[68]	5
D15	Changes in development stages	[18],[41],[80],[84]	4
D16	<i>Trade-off between ethics and economics</i>	[36],[67],[80],[68]	4
D17	Identifying privacy requirements	[18],[13],[89],[69]	4
D18	Impact on application usability	[85]	1

D1) Lack of awareness of the law: This was the main challenge identified in the SLR, so it covers two situations: the lack of awareness about the need to implement privacy in software (E13[15], E17[44], E16[72]); and the low or no knowledge about the legislation, i.e. the scarcity of theoretical knowledge in relation to the law in force (E10[18], E43[7], [78]). Peixoto et al. (E38[89]) reported that, even though developers have empirical knowledge about privacy, the major obstacle is knowing how to interpret the privacy requirements, since most of them have no formal knowledge about privacy and the LGPD. Thus, the practices that organizations have adopted in order to solve this challenge is through training and mentoring for developers (E39[90]), including seminars (E13[15]).

D2) Translating the law into a technical context: A major problem pointed out by developers from different regions (subject to various privacy laws) is the reading of expressly theoretical standards, in which there is no specification of techniques for achieving compliance (E45[94], E39[90], E26[17]). Thus, as the application of methods depends on the developer's prior knowledge (E39[90], E24[78]), the translation of legislative requirements into the privacy context within a specific scope of the

organization is of profound technical complexity and many developers don't feel comfortable with it (E39[90]). Not only that, but developers also have obstacles when it comes to processes involving data anonymization and automation (E35[86]). To make up for the lack of specification of techniques in laws, the adoption of more specific frameworks is a common solution for developers (E11[4]), since it allows the rules of current legislation to be combined with the chosen framework (E27[79]). In addition, Kuhlreiber et al. (E27[79]) added that the use of tools that analyze data flow and identify sensitive data - such as FlowFence, SainT and Databox - contribute in this respect.

D3) Budget restrictions: This is a common obstacle that only affects organizations, i.e. developers have little or no influence over it (E46[95], E29[80]). About a year after the GDPR came into force, Teixeira et al. (E46[95]) showed in their study that the process of complying with the law is costly and time-consuming, as it requires recurring financial and human resources, although organizations have them to a limited extent (E29[80], E43[7]). Poritskiy et al. (E33[84]) also associated security operations with the increase in organizations' budgets, i.e. the level of data privacy and security can be closely linked to the capital available to guarantee it. For small and medium-sized companies, this challenge is even more critical (E40[91]) and one solution proposed by Brodin et al. (E34[85]) would be the use of proactive privacy design, which reveals the contrast with the solution elaborated by Ayala-Rivera (E16[72]), in which solution requirements link GDPR standards and business requirements.

D4) Lack of staff with expertise: This differs from the challenge of lack of knowledge of the legislation for the following reason: in this context, companies need additional administrative staff (E45[94]) and also specialized DPO staff (E36[87], E46[95]). That said, the lack of a team with expertise in current legislation can lead to ineffective risk assessment in data protection [74] and, with regard to Brazilian legislation, the guidelines of the LGPD Good Practice Guide may not be fully respected (E36[87]). A relevant solution, as mentioned above, is the appointment of a DPO within the organization itself (E36[87], E46[95]) and, in the case of the GDPR, the adoption of a controller even makes it possible to restrict the flow of data in the system (E27[79]).

D5) Organizational structure: Horstmann et al. (E37[88]) pointed out that a company's privacy experts often do not understand the software developers, and vice versa. This means that, because of this communication barrier (established in the organization's structure), developers may not be able to implement adequate privacy in their applications, since they do not have the respective knowledge to do so.

codes of conduct. In addition, it is not uncommon for the organization itself to set limitations for its employees (E43[7], E10[18]), so that regulatory compliance is not achieved due to a lack of communication between the organization's teams (E26[17]). Davier et al. (E26[17]) stated that knowledge management within a company is the key to effective internal organization and legally compliant information processing. In addition, communication projects such as a strategic information systems plan (E6[67]) or the Institutional Data Privacy Program (E36[87]) can adapt organizations and improve the culture practiced.

D6) Ambiguity of the law: Aljerais et al. (E17[44]) elucidated that a large part of developers will certainly present difficulties in complying with regulations when they are vague, since it makes the process of extracting and implementing these legal requirements difficult. Not only that, but since the requirements are not addressed in simple and specific language, they are open to multiple interpretations (E12[70], E29[80]), which can guarantee a certain level of privacy, but not always what is desired by the legislation. Aljerais et al. (E17[44]) also propose solutions to the problem of ambiguity in legislation, such as a mapping between privacy law and privacy by design schemes (covered in Section 2.2), as well as the use of design standards such as encryption using a user-managed key, measurement obfuscation with the addition of noise (to prevent sensitive data leakage) and a data breach notification standard.

D7) Lack of standardization of techniques/tools: The study proposed by Tahaei et al. (E39[90]) showed that there is a lack of standardization and evaluation metrics, since the conceptualization of privacy is volatile, i.e., although there are taxonomies and frameworks that conceptualize how privacy should be implemented, there is no consideration among all of them. To highlight this point, studies show that the decision on privacy depends on each project (E38[89]) and the available legislation does not provide specific guidelines on the technologies to be used, meaning that organizations must find their own specific solutions (E46[95]). In short, there is no standardization of techniques, tools or methodologies adopted to achieve compliance with legislation, and it is a challenge to establish appropriate and specific design guidelines (E10[18], E26[17], E43[7], E51[97], E53[98]). The studies highlighted possible solutions, such as being guided by the guidelines of the application's publishing platform (E53[98]).

D8) Lack of security/privacy policy: Drawing up a consent form and a security policy is a challenge that is still neglected by organizations today (E10[18], E29[80], E35[86]). The work

de Freitas et al. (E40[91]) pointed out that most of the companies involved did not have a record of security measures and, furthermore, no company had a procedure for notifying the authority in the event of a personal data breach. In addition to negligence on the part of the organizations, the challenge may come from the developer themselves, since when they use third-party libraries, they don't have a complete understanding of their applications and it makes it impossible to properly draw up a privacy policy (E50[37]). That said, it is possible to solve the problem by drawing up transparent terms of use, as well as reviewing the legal bases so that an effective and up-to-date security policy can be created (E43[7]), in addition to techniques such as Third-Party Tracking and API Configurations (E52[16]).

D9) Relationship with the user: Under current legislation, the data subject (usually the user of an application) is granted various rights - such as portability, rectification and deletion of information - which actively influence the processing of their personal data (E29[80], E33[84]). In addition, the difficulty in the relationship between the user and the organization or part of the developers was identified as a challenge in the studies, even in the consent process, since there is a portion of users who are indifferent to the benefits of privacy (E43[7], E39[90]). In addition, developers find it very difficult to implement transparency - through privacy policies and feedback systems - in software, which further highlights the challenge (E44[93]). However, the study proposed by Wiefeling et al. (E44[93]) showed that renowned companies such as Microsoft and Google already mitigate this problem through self-service tools, or similarly, privacy dashboards.

D10) Prioritization of functional requirements: With regard to the prioritization of functional requirements by developers, the studies pointed to a number of factors to be taken into consideration, such as the reduction in system performance (E11[4], E45[94]), the tight deadlines for implementing effective security (E29[80]) or even the difficulty in implementing non-functional requirements (E43[7]). The fact is that there is an identified tension between priorities (E39[90]) and the prioritization of functional requirements to the detriment of security and privacy is considered a relevant challenge in the context of compliance with privacy legislation (E24[78]). When the problem is one of time, the application of automated tests can increase the importance given to non-functional requirements and the use of methods that contribute to the rapid updating of applications and effective feedback can also motivate developers to improve both categories of requirements (E21[41]).

D11) Uncertainty of organizational processes: When it comes to the relationship between organization and developer, it is likely that the latter will not always know all the organizational processes. This relationship is even more problematic, since it is necessary for all the stages of processing personal data to be in accordance with current legislation, which leads to challenges in adapting backups (E11[4]), establishing audits of systems and processes (E33[84]) and using cloud services (E49[60]) (which also depend on where the data is physically stored). Based on this, a good starting point for mitigating the risks of uncertainty is through access logs when it comes to data processing and opting for cloud providers that are compatible and guarantee compliance with current legislation (E11[4]).

D12) Difficulties with third-party services: Alomar et al. (E50[37]) show that a large part of the problems relating to privacy stem from the use of third-party Software Development Kits (SDKs). This means that, even if an application has been implemented natively in compliance with current legislation, by adopting SDKs the developer will not have the guarantee that compliance has been maintained (and companies often don't even analyze this type of contract and the guarantee of compliance (E40[91])), which elucidates a new class of challenges that even address the management of contracting processes (E11[4], E33[84]). As such, one of the main challenges pointed out by the developers is navigating the privacy implications of these libraries and, likewise, it is not yet clear how the libraries will process personal data (E52[16], E53[98]). Solutions that address the challenge include prioritizing libraries from prominent providers and, where possible, not sharing data that is not absolutely necessary with third parties (E53[98]).

D13) Shortage of guides/tools: As discussed above, privacy legislation presents points of ambiguity and it is difficult to translate legislation into a technical context, guides and tools contribute to the compliance process. However, the lack of specific guides for applying privacy in a software context is a problem highlighted by Brazilian and European developers (E24[78], E43[7]). Ekambaranathan et al. (E53[98]) identified, through interviews, that many application developers had difficulties finding adequate and specific design guidelines, and that when they did, the support was insufficient for smaller companies. Therefore, solutions such as focusing on a good user experience and consulting professionals in the absence of guides and tools were elucidated in the work.

D14) International data processing: With regard to organizations

that deal with people's data globally, a challenge is identified regarding which current legislation to prioritize (E13[15]). As discussed in RQ.1, the laws have many points of divergence, which can lead to expectations of a judicial response and contractual difficulties, especially when it comes to small and medium-sized companies (E13[15], E40[91]). Of course, all the other challenges are added to this one, since a common solution must be found to the difficulties of ensuring compliance with multiple laws. In practical terms, a good place to start is mapping and then analyzing the data flow (E13[15]), and the use of tools and automation can facilitate the technical compliance process.

D15) Changes in the development stages: In the process of developing a product, it is common for changes to occur in some of the stages, ranging from infrastructure and data growth to readjustments of systems to make them more compatible in a certain aspect (E10[18], E29[80]). Although these changes are sometimes necessary, it is true that they increase technical complexity and require reformulations of techniques that implement privacy in software (E29[80]). Li et al. (E21[41]) explained the challenge of balancing GDPR compliance in a competitive data business environment and, based on this, one solution pointed out in the study is the use of continuous software engineering, since it combines rapid updates and feedback, and enables the accelerated correction of points of non-compliance (identified in the feedback).

D16) Ethics vs. economics trade-off: The obstacle that any acting organization will encounter is finding the balance between respecting privacy and prioritizing corporate freedom (E5[36]). Since a company's primary objective is economic, given the nature of the business (E29[80]), the focus on privacy and the protection of personal data can be placed on a low priority agenda (E6[67]), even if there are laws requiring compliance. Rocha et al. (E43[7]) showed that organizations must consider, on an economic level, the possible administrative sanctions in the event of non-compliance with legislation and that reduced reliability on the part of customers causes a competitive disadvantage in the long term, which could lead to financial losses for the organization.

D17) Identifying privacy requirements: As mentioned earlier, developers have an empirical knowledge of privacy, but identifying an application's privacy requirements in the light of data protection legislation is a complex task (E38[89]). Therefore, it is necessary to use an artifice to help comply with the law in force, such as the specification of User Stories, in order to facilitate the requirements analysis stage (E10[18]). Furthermore, as a technique used in agile teams, a possible solution would be to use

Design Thinking tools in the requirements elicitation stage (E9[69]), with the same intent.

D18) Impact on the usability of the application: This is a problem for small and medium-sized businesses, since if the processing power of the data is not sufficient, the addition of a privacy and data protection framework could reduce the performance of the system or make it impossible to use an application (E34[85]). It is recommended to use specific frameworks as early as possible, i.e. in the application design process (E34[85]), in order to estimate and avoid performance risks.

RQ.2 Summary: The main challenges for ensuring compliance are related to the process of understanding the law. A massive amount of developers and organizations still have difficulty understanding the theory of the law and how to apply it in a technical context. Restrictions imposed by organizations and a lack of suitable material to assist were also identified as major challenges.